

REINCARNATE

D6.3 – REINCARNATE Impact Assessment and Exploitation Interim

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Abstract

Exploitation within the Reincarnate project focuses on maximizing the impact and value of research outcomes generated from EU projects, creating tangible benefits for society, industry, and the economy. Developing business models plays a crucial role in translating these research outcomes into practical applications and commercial opportunities. Traditionally, business models focused on maximizing profits without considering environmental and social impacts. However, the Circular Economy (CE) paradigm necessitates new concepts and tools to support sustainable business practices. This report highlights the importance of a structured methodology with a focus on Circular Economy Business Models (CEBMs) to enable the regeneration of finite natural resources and maintain products, components, and materials at their highest value and utility. Acknowledging this, the Reincarnate Exploitation Methodology integrates the R2PI (Transition from Linear 2 Circular) framework, tailored specifically for developing CEBMs. This approach includes eight strategic steps, ensuring results from each assessment are effectively integrated and utilized for informed decision making. Moreover, recognizing the complexities of integrating CEBM principles into digital platforms, our project utilized the Bosch IoT Lab’s Platform Navigator to tailor tools specifically for dematerialized assets. The report begins by identifying the characteristics of the Key Exploitable Assets (KEAs) within the project, which form the basis for business model development. It provides detailed description of the Reincarnate Exploitation Methodology steps, presenting the outcomes of Steps 1 and 2 for selected KEAs, along with results from the application of the Platform Navigator on Circular Potential Information Model (CP-IM) system. Furthermore, it elaborates on the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) protection and knowledge management plan. The report concludes by introducing technical and process innovations, advancing technologies to proven solutions at the system or sub-system level.

Keywords:

Circular Economy (CE), Circular Economy Business Models (CEBMs), Business canvas, Exploitation

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
BMC	Business Model Canvas
C&DW	Construction and Demolition Waste
C2C	Cradle-to-cradle
CBM	Circular Business Model
CE	Circular Economy
CEBMs	Circular Economy Business Models
CP-IM	Circular Potential Information Management
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
KEAs	Key Exploitation Activities

KEAs	Key Exploitable Assets
LCA	Life-cycle Assessment
LCC	Life-cycle Cost
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
R2PI	tRansition from Linear 2 Circular: Policy and Innovation
RaaS	Robot as a Service
SaaS	Software as a Service
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work Package
XaaS	Anything as a Service

Reincarnate project

The average lifespan of a building is 39 years¹, and factors such as obsolescence and technical limitations often lead to demolition. Consequently, a significant amount of construction and demolition waste (CDW) is generated. Effectively reducing construction waste requires addressing two key aspects: 1) preventing existing buildings from becoming functionally or financially obsolete, and 2) upgrading buildings and their components to extend their lifetime. Despite good intentions, studies have shown that upgradability as a product lifetime extension strategy is limited and reusing entire buildings, building products, or materials in different settings is challenging. These challenges have resulted in a limited use of secondary materials in the building sector². Despite high recycling rates, CDW recycling often leads to downcycling.

Reincarnate aims to advance circular economy practices in the European construction industry by extending the life cycle of buildings, products, and materials, aiming to reduce CDW by 80%, increase reusability by promoting circular economy principles, and lower sector emissions by 70%.

Through the Circular Potential Information Management (CP-IM) platform and associated innovations, Reincarnate will leverage digital technologies like digital twin representation, artificial intelligence, and robotic automation. Building upon three empirically proven social science insights, the project aims to foster the widespread adoption of reused high-quality construction products and materials. Additionally, it will develop business eco-system frameworks to connect actors within sustainable value chains.

Reincarnate's impact will be demonstrated through eleven real-world projects and value chains. Business process guidelines and an e-learning platform will be developed to facilitate the dissemination and exploitation of Reincarnate's results, ultimately contributing to the advancement of circular economy practices in the European construction industry.

¹ Muresan et al. 2021 - Sustainability through reuse

² Van den Berg, Voordijk, Adriaanse (2020). Recovering building elements for reuse (or not) – Ethnographic insights into selective demolition practices. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 256.

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1. Introduction

This report is the result of Task 6.3, 'Impact, Exploitation and Sustainability,' which is part of Work Package 6, 'Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation' (Figure 1). It is structured to initially provide background and highlight the importance of the exploitation process. The document presents a brief literature review, detailing state-of-the-art business model development approaches for circularity. It proceeds with an in-depth explanation of the established methodology in Transition from Linear 2 Circular: Policy and Innovation (R2PI) project, elaborating on its application within the Reincarnate project. The report illustrates how various tools are employed within this methodology to develop Circular Economy Business Models (CEBMs). Consequently, it outlines the identified exploitation activities and presents preliminary results from the steps taken, as well as initial business models for the identified key exploitable results. Moreover, it elaborates on the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) protection and the knowledge management plan. Lastly, the report concludes by listing the potential new Key Exploitable Assets (KEAs).

Figure 1: The relationship between different work packages.

2. Methodology

This section outlines how circular economy principles were integrated into our project's business models. It begins with a general definition and the purpose of exploitation processes, followed by a step-by-step explanation of the business model development process. Next, it provides a brief overview of existing methodologies tailored for circular business models. It then delves into our chosen methodology for business model development, emphasizing the R2PI framework as the foundational tool for developing business models for Reincarnate key exploitable results.

Given that our services will be delivered digitally, we also utilize The Platform Navigator methodology [1] to develop a business model for the Circular Potential Information Model (CPIM) platform, as this methodology is specifically designed to guide the development and implementation of platform-based business models. In the following sections, we will present the outcomes derived from the implementation of these methodologies.

2.1. Exploitation process

Exploitation in the context of Reincarnate project refers to the process of maximizing the impact and value of research outcomes generated within EU projects. It involves leveraging these outcomes to create tangible benefits for society, industry, and the economy. Exploitation is crucial in EU projects as it ensures that the investments made in research and innovation yield meaningful results and contribute to addressing societal challenges.

In this context, developing **business models** is essential to translate research outcomes into practical applications and commercial opportunities. Business models provide a structured approach for identifying and capturing value from project results, guiding the development of strategies for market entry, revenue generation, and sustainable growth. They help project consortia to understand the market dynamics, identify potential customers, and tailor their offerings to meet specific needs and preferences. Moreover, business models enable project consortia to assess the feasibility and viability of their innovations, identify potential risks and challenges, and develop strategies to mitigate them.

2.2. Development of the new business models

The process of developing a new business model entails several crucial steps, each contributing to the overall success of the venture. These steps are illustrated in Figure 2 and are fundamental to the strategic planning and execution of the business model.

Identification of Key Exploitable Results/Assets (KERs): The process starts with identifying the key exploitable results generated through research and innovation. These results represent the core innovations, technologies, or solutions that have the potential for commercialization or societal impact.

Market Analysis: Conducting a thorough market analysis is essential to understand the dynamics, trends, and opportunities within the target market. This step involves assessing market demand, competition, regulatory landscape, and potential barriers to entry.

Target Group Definition: Defining the target group or customer segments is crucial for tailoring the business model to meet specific customer needs and preferences. This step involves identifying the characteristics, behaviours, and pain points of the target audience to inform product development and marketing strategies.

Development of Exploitation Models: Developing exploitation models involves exploring different pathways for monetizing the key exploitable results. This may include strategies such as licensing, product sales, subscription models, or strategic partnerships. The goal is to identify the most effective and sustainable approach for capturing value from the innovations.

Consideration of Intellectual Property (IP): Intellectual property considerations play a significant role in shaping the business model. This step involves assessing the IP landscape, securing necessary patents or copyrights, and establishing strategies for protecting and leveraging intellectual assets to maintain a competitive advantage in the market.

Formulation of the Business Model: The final step is the formulation of the business model, which integrates insights from the previous steps into a cohesive framework for value creation and delivery. This includes defining the value proposition, revenue streams, distribution channels, cost structure, and key partnerships necessary to bring the innovation to market successfully.

Each of these steps is interconnected and builds upon the insights gained from the preceding stages. By systematically progressing through these steps, businesses can

develop robust and sustainable business models that maximize the potential of their key exploitable results and drive long-term success in the marketplace.

Figure 2: Major steps towards the development of a new business model.

2.3. Key Exploitable Asset (KEA) Characterization Template

Identifying a key exploitable result is the initial step to develop a proper business model and the development and strategic management of new business models. Drawing on experiences from projects such as Precept³ and SmartLivingEPC⁴, a comprehensive template was created to identify and describe the KEAs in the Reincarnate project, as shown in Table 1. The characterization template is structured to include details regarding each KEA. It lists the KEA's type and name along with a brief description and outlines the exploitation plans, detailing the development stages of the product or service derived from the KEA. It also incorporates essential elements such as the KEA manager, the level of innovation, the expected Technology Readiness Level (TRL), and any pilot testing or validation that has been conducted. Additionally, the template addresses basic market and potential customer information, alongside plans for Intellectual Property (IP) protection, and includes a section on dissemination, outlining planned actions and identifying the target audience.

Table 1: KEA Characterization Table.

KEA Name	
Type, Name Short Description	Exploitation Information
Type*: Name:	KEA Manager: Innovation Level**: Expected TRL: Pilot test/ validation:

³ <https://www.precept-project.eu/>

⁴ <https://www.smartlivingepc.eu/en>

<p>Ownership:</p> <p>Description:</p>	<p><u>Which previous knowledge/expertise/technology/IP etc. has been leveraged for this KEA?</u></p> <p><u>Why Innovative/ Exploitable?</u></p> <p><u>Which are the input data/information? Which are the output data/information?</u></p> <p><u>Mainly for ICT/technological solutions: any relevant aspects re. interoperability to be mentioned?</u></p> <p><u>Exploitation Vision:</u> <i>Describe here the expected potential of exploitation and the exploitation vision for the ER.</i></p> <p><u>Actions:</u> <i>Describe here the KEA's progress done, until today, from the beginning of the project</i></p> <p><u>IP Protection Strategy:</u></p> <p style="background-color: #e0f0ff;">Dissemination Information</p> <p><u>Which dissemination actions do you plan to promote this KEA?</u></p> <p><u>What is the audience that can make use this KEA and that should be targeted by dissemination actions?</u></p>
<p>Market Analysis & Market Landscape: <i>On which markets would you like to offer the new or improved product/services? offer te products produced by the new or improved process?</i></p> <p>Please indicate market segment, countries of interest, companies of interest.</p>	
<p><i>*Could be S/W, Software as a Service (SaaS), Robot as a Service (RaaS), process, methodology, service knowledge etc.</i></p> <p><i>**The innovation levels range from Level 1, Standard, involving solutions with well-known methods, to Level 2, Improvement, which enhances existing systems within the same industry. Level 3, Within Paradigm,</i></p>	

proposes improvements using method methods from other fields. **Level 4, Outside Paradigm**, focuses on creating new systems through scientific solutions rather than technology. **Level 5, Discovery**, pioneers new systems based on major discoveries and new sciences.

2.4. Strategic management of a business model

After identifying a key exploitable asset, the business model canvas (BMC) can be utilized as a strategic management tool, providing a structured and visual framework for developing and analyzing new business models. BMC was introduced by Alexander Osterwalder and Yves Pigneur in their book "Business Model Generation" in 2010[2]. As illustrated in Figure 3, the BMC consists of nine building blocks that represent the key elements of a business model, including customer segments, value proposition, channels, customer relationships, revenue streams, key resources, key activities, key partnerships, and cost structure. By encapsulating key elements in a single visual format, the BMC provides a holistic overview of how a business creates, delivers, and captures value. It enables stakeholders to align around the organization's goals, identify areas for improvement, and mitigate risks. The BMC also promotes iterative development, allowing to experiment with different strategies and adapt to market feedback quickly. Its visual nature makes it an effective communication tool, facilitating collaboration and buy-in from internal and external stakeholders. Overall, the BMC helps businesses achieve clarity, focus, and alignment in their strategy, driving sustainable growth and success in the marketplace.

Figure 3: Nine building blocks of a business model canvas.

2.5. Circular economy business models

At the time when the Business Model Canvas was developed, circularity and sustainability were not as central to business practices as they are today. Traditional business models often focused primarily on maximizing profits without considering the environmental and social impacts of their operations. However, in recent years, there has been a growing recognition of the importance of circularity and sustainability in business practices. As a result, business models have evolved to integrate principles of circular economy and sustainability, aiming to minimize waste, maximize resource efficiency, and create positive social and environmental outcomes.

The circular economy paradigm is distinct from the conventional linear model of production, which follows an extraction-production-use-disposal sequence and heavily depends on fossil fuels. Unlike the business models within the linear economy, circular business models shift the focus from earning profits through the sale of products to making profits by managing the continuous flow of materials and products over time. Consequently, this paradigm necessitates the development of novel concepts and tools to adequately describe and support it. Particularly at the product design level and within the strategic framework of business model innovation, establishing a more coherent terminology is crucial to effectively facilitate the transition of businesses toward circular model [3]. Recognizing these needs, our project has been motivated to apply a methodology that utilizes the circular economy business model perspective for our Key Exploitable Assets (KEAs) and potentially for our innovations. This approach aligns with the broader movement towards sustainability and responsible resource management, ensuring that our practices not only meet current environmental and economic challenges but also set a precedent for future developments.

Figure 4: Circular Business Model Constructs adapted from [4].

In order to adopt a relevant methodology, an examination has been conducted to comprehend the current landscape of **Circular Business Model (CBM)** or **Circular Economy Business Model (CEBM)** research and to identify the main barriers and gaps in the field. This analysis helps to better define our requirements and criteria for adopting an existing methodology. As presented in [4] and summarized in (Figure 4), the study discusses the definitional ambiguity characterizing the field, with sixteen different definitions proposed, illustrating a clear lack of consensus. A diverse range of constructs such as *archetypes*, *canvasses*, *categories*, *frameworks*, and *taxonomies* have been put forward to categorize and classify CBMs. However, many of these constructs lack practical validation and do not provide comprehensive guidance for business model implementation, which is critical for the transition from theory to practice. As explained by the author, the extensive variety of these constructs potentially obscures the essential nature of CBMs, focusing disproportionately on their diverse functional forms at the expense of a unified conceptual foundation. The necessity for a coherent terminology and a consensus on definitions and frameworks is emphasized as essential for creating a shared discourse that supports the practical implementation of CBMs. Without this clarity, the fundamental principles of CBMs risk being overlooked, hindering their effective integration into business practices [4].

In order to overcome this barrier, we considered the ISO/DIS 59000 series and specifically ISO 59010 [5], as one of the primary resources before selecting our tools and methodologies in the project. This standard provides a unified **business-oriented** guidance on achieving CE by setting goals, identifying circularity aspects to address, and initiating actions. However, while the standard offers extensive guidance, it does not explicitly include tools such as canvases or other constructs that are directly applicable to our specific needs. Moreover, due to its strong focus on transitioning to CEBMs at an organizational level rather than explicitly at the product or innovation level, we decided to use it as a reference for aligning structurally and ontologically with our chosen methodology, but not as our primary resource for developing the CEBMs.

Considering the guidelines indicated in ISO 59010 and in conjunction with the previously mentioned barriers and gaps, we established a set of selection criteria for our exploitation methodology. These criteria include *flexibility*, emphasizing adaptability and the capability to integrate with other tools; *transparency* in methodology application; *validation* in real-world practice. This approach ensures that the methodologies we adopt are not only aligned with ISO standards but also robust enough to address the diverse requirements inherent in implementing CEBMs.

With the above-mentioned set of criteria, we came across **Transition from Linear 2 Circular: Policy and Innovation (R2PI)** Project, which provides a structured approach for integrating circular economy principles into business models. In the following sections, we will provide a brief overview of the R2PI framework and explain how we have adapted its methodology to develop our business canvases.

Moreover, recognizing the complexities of integrating circular economy business model principles into **digital** platforms, our project explored tools tailored for digital products. Our approach was to utilize the **Bosch IoT Lab's Platform Navigator**⁵, which is specifically designed to aid the development of platform-based business models. This tool aligns well with our needs by offering a structured and interactive approach to incorporate circular economy principles into digital platforms effectively.

This integrated approach ensures that our methodologies are not only comprehensive but also adaptable to the evolving needs of both tangible and digital products in the circular economy.

⁵ <https://www.iot-lab.ch/projects-businessmodels/platform-navigator/>

2.5.1. R2PI framework

The R2PI project (Transition from Linear to Circular: Policy and Innovation), supported by the EU, lays a solid foundation, and offers valuable insights into circular economy business models. The international consortium of R2PI includes 16 partners from 9 Member States and Associated Countries⁶. Initially, more than 300 potential organizations across various sectors including water, construction, electronics, food, plastics, and textiles were evaluated in the project. This led to a shortlist of approximately 50 case study candidates that align with the EU's circular economy strategy. The subsequent refinement process resulted in the selection of 18 final demonstration cases, aimed at ensuring broad geographical representation and demonstrable benefits.

The Circular Economy (CE) concept proposed in R2PI considers profitability, social aspects, efficiency, products as services, and operational tools and guidelines as enabling factors or framing conditions. The first of these framing conditions is a business model perspective. According to R2PI, a prerequisite for the successful implementation of CEBMs is their profitability for companies. Although not being part of the core characteristics of a CE, profitability has thus to be a central focus in the development of CEBM [6]. Overall, their strong business model focus comes from the fact that they consider it as one of the main enablers of the CE.

The following content aims to provide the working definition of the CEBM by deriving it from its building blocks, as illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5: CEBM Building Blocks, illustration by authors.

Material Pathways & Cycles:

The definition of CEBM begins by recognizing the desired outcomes of CE from the perspective of business models. The core outcome, within the specified system boundary, the business models of organizations in a value chain must facilitate the

⁶ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/730378>

regeneration of finite natural resources while ensuring that products, components, and materials retain their highest value and utility. Thus, the initial step involves aligning the fundamental CE outcomes with what CEBMs aim to deliver. Figure 6 depicts the material pathways and cycles that serve as the foundation for defining the expected outcomes of CEBMs within a system boundary [6]:

Figure 6: Material Flow Mapping adapted from [6].

- **Re-use:** Products are utilized repeatedly by various end-users throughout their functional lifespan.
- **Re-condition:** Involves fixing faults or enhancing the aesthetic of a product without extending a new warranty, which includes both repairing any damage to restore functionality and refurbishing to meet aesthetic standards.
- **Re-make:** Also referred to as 'remanufacturing' or 'reman', this process includes various manufacturing steps applied to a product or part at the end of its cycle to restore its performance to like-new or better condition, accompanied by a corresponding warranty.
- **Resource recovery:** Materials or products at the end of their lifecycle are reclaimed and reintroduced as inputs into various value chains. This process encompasses both closed-loop recycling, where materials are recycled within the same value chain while preserving their quality for repeated use, and open-loop recycling, where materials are transferred to different value chains for single-use recycling, often described as a 'cascade.' This cascade includes up-cycling, where end-of-life

materials are transformed into products of higher value, and down-cycling, where they are converted into products of lesser value.

- **Circular sourcing:** Sourcing involves utilizing recycled or renewable materials that can be reintegrated into either the technical or biological cycles. This process includes using materials reclaimed from end-of-life products rather than virgin materials from finite resources for the technical cycle, and employing renewable or bio-based materials that are suitable for return to the biological cycle.
- **Co-product recovery:** Residual or secondary outputs from one process or value chain are repurposed as inputs for another, contributing to resource efficiency. This transformation includes direct use or industrial symbiosis, where byproducts from one process serve as feedstock for another, often within close geographic proximity to minimize transportation costs. Additionally, indirect use involves converting outputs, typically considered waste, into valuable commodities or feedstock for different processes, such as using fly-ash from coal combustion as clinker in cement production, with these materials often traded in secondary markets [6].

Circular Economy Business Model Patterns (CEBMs):

In the R2PI methodology, *circular pathways* are defined through a direct mapping of the *material pathways*, except for “access and performance”. Consequently, the brief definitions we previously established above are applicable to these circular pathways. This mapping process facilitates the transition of these elements to what are termed *business model patterns*, which is crucial in achieving a clear definition for CEBMs.

A “business model pattern,” also known as an archetype, outlines a specific configuration of business model operations. To creating circular material flows, **seven** CEBM patterns have been defined. These patterns are categorized based on *distinct set of business model dynamics* and their position within a product's life cycle, as illustrated in Figure 7. Among these, the “Access” and “Performance” models do not inherently embody circularity but, when integrated with other models, they significantly boost the circular benefits and value. Each of the seven CEBM patterns has been developed into individual frameworks, adapting the Business Model Canvas to incorporate circular economy principles. This adaptation introduces guiding prompts within each of the nine canvas elements (see Figure 8), serving as examples of potential business models for each of the seven *CEBM Patterns* [6].

Figure 7: CEBM Patterns adapted from [6].

Mapping CEBM patterns to Canvases:

Each of the seven CEBM patterns is characterized by a distinct combination of business model elements that collectively yield a CE outcome. In Figure 8, the Business Model Canvas (BMC) presented differs from the conventional format by including additional elements for *Social* and *Environmental* impacts, which the R2PI team refers to as the '9+2' model. Although the traditional BMC is a well-established and proven framework, it does not explicitly account for the value created or destroyed in environmental, social, and other dimensions, nor is it suited to mapping the complexities of material flows. To overcome these limitations, the canvas has been adapted by integrating both positive and negative social and environmental impacts and costs. These adaptations are utilized across all CEBM canvases (Figure 20 to Figure 26). Finally, a CEBM is defined as one which *“creates, delivers, and captures value in a manner that is compatible with and enables the regeneration of finite natural resources; and keeping products, components, and materials at their highest value and utility within a relevant system boundary”* ([6], p. 40).

Source: R2Pi Project

Figure 8: Adjusted Business Canvas by R2PI (9+2) [7].

2.6. Reincarnate exploitation process based on R2PI Methodology

As illustrated in the Figure 9, we sought an alignment between the 9R strategies and R2PI at the ontological level, linking us to their core concepts of CEBM development.

⁷ The number on the canvas have been adjusted by BMO for clarification.

Figure 9: Strategic alignment between 9R and R2PI.

Following this strategic alignment, at this stage, we directed our focus to the 'Understand' and 'Innovate' stages of development of the process (Design, understand, innovate, validate, deliver, and evaluate [7]). In these stages, we employed a range of tools from R2PI, specifically tailored to suit the Reincarnate Exploitation Methodology. Our approach involved not only customizing the sequence of steps but also refining the interactions and iterations between them. This customization ensures that the results of each assessment are effectively integrated and utilized to make informed decisions throughout the CEBM development.

Consequently, our approach is structured through eight strategic steps that can be seen in Figure 10 designed to embed circular economy business model practices into our project. In **Steps 1 and 2**, our goal is to establish the AS-IS business model canvas for selected KEAs and innovations based on the initial TRL. **Steps 3 through 6** are focused primarily on the development of these business model canvases towards a higher TRL. **Steps 7 and 8** shift our focus towards the practical realization of the business models, examining the value network and exploring potential partnerships in greater detail.

Figure 10: REINCARNATE Exploitation Roadmap.

2.6.1. Step 1: Identification of CEBM patterns

This step involves the identification of CEBM patterns. According to the R2PI methodology, the identification of Circular Economy Business Model (CEBM) patterns involves a two-step process [7]. In this approach, we analyse these patterns from the perspective of Reincarnate's KEAs. The activities are as follows:

- 1.1) **Applicability of CEBM Patterns:** We assess which of the seven identified CEBM patterns can be applied and integrated into the business model of the KEA. This step aims to initially identify which circular economy aspects are most relevant and how they can be detailed further when reviewing the foundational components of the business model, such as its canvas elements.
- 1.2) **Relationship with the Value Chain/Network:** We determine which aspects of the CEBM patterns are influenced by or support the dynamics within the wider value chain or network. This requires only a preliminary description, which will be elaborated upon during the value flow mapping process.

2.6.2. Step 2: Development of Business Model Canvas

This step is divided into two main tasks:

- 2.1) **KEA owners** will reflect on the CEBM canvas questions (Appendix 7.1.2) internally, applying the identified CEBM pattern to the corresponding asset.
- 2.2) Combining the results to further obtain the **AS-IS business model canvas** through an online interactive workshop. The primary goal of this internal discussion, guided by the *questions outlined in the following section*, is to promote "*Circular Business Model Thinking*".

Figure 11: REINCARNATE Interactive Workshop Series for KEA 2 & 3.

2.6.3. Step 3: Business Model Assessment

In this step, KEA and innovation owners assess and rate the AS-IS business model canvas that is obtained in the previous step, to generate reflective insights for further development.

- 3.1 – Business Model Assessment Workshop:** A workshop will be designed in collaboration with TUB to validate the assumptions made while developing the AS-IS business model canvases. During the workshop, various business models will be iterated upon based on input from market experts invited to participate. The workshop will begin with one initial business model and generate two or three alternative models. Experts will have opportunity to contribute their market expertise and insights. By the end of the workshop, a consensus will be reached on the most promising business model and the most relevant customer

segments for the technology. Additionally, the workshop will help define the potential Minimum Viable Product (MVP), highlighting the key features of the existing technology that need further development. Overall, this process will ensure that the correct customer segments are identified and that the assumptions regarding the problems are validated. Throughout the workshop, proven methods such as the Lean Startup approach will be utilized [8].

- **3.2 – Business Model Circularity Assessment:** The assessment is conducted internally, using the Business Circularity Assessment tool (Figure 18 [7]), which draws on extensive research into methods for evaluating circularity at *product*, *business model*, and *system* levels. This encompasses the conceptualization of CEBMs and incorporates several product metrics validated using the Cradle-to-Cradle (C2C)⁸ Institute's methodology. The tool is designed to encourage users to critically assess their existing business models from a circular perspective [9]. It includes *31 statements* that help assess the current (or AS-IS) business models' tendencies towards either circular or linear.

Overall, in this step, the KEA and innovation owners will assess their business models to gain insights and ensure alignment with CE principles.

2.6.4. Step 4: Evaluation of the Circularity Assessment Results

In this step, DMO evaluates the results of the Business Model Circularity Assessment. The primary task is to analyse the assessment outputs to determine the CEBM pattern ranking and to generate element-wise business canvas priority heat-map. This analysis leverages a detailed table, presented in Figure 19 [7], which correlates each statement from Business Model Circularity Assessment with multiple CEBM patterns. Additionally, on the right-hand side of the table, each statement is mapped to a priority heat-map corresponding to each element in the business model canvas. This mapping acts as a form of dictionary, not only linking assessment statements to CEBM patterns but also assigning a prioritization level to each business model canvas element.

As part of the process, by aggregating the Business Model Circularity Assessment scores in a specific manner, we aim to achieve a ranked output of CEBM patterns (Figure 12). Essentially, higher confidence in a specific assessment response, and their cumulative scores with respect to each CEBM pattern, will help to identify the most relevant or one

⁸ <https://c2ccertified.org/>

of the most relevant CEBM patterns for each KEA or innovation. This process, customized by DMO, could be crucial for making informed decisions regarding both the validation of identified CEBM patterns and the discovery of potential new ones.

Furthermore, the results from these priority heat-maps could be significant in refining the business model canvas (will then be denoted as CEBM canvases) for each KEA. The proposed methodology highlights key success factors, which will be elaborated upon in the following section, thereby informing targeted improvements to specific elements of the business model canvas [7].

	Key partners	Key activities	Key resources	Value proposition	Customer relationships	Channels	Customer segments	Cost structure	Revenue streams
#1	0.5018	0.4053	0.3375	0.223	0.2668	0	0.1022	0.5326	0.3994
#2	0.1382	0.1916	0.3467	0.3707	0.5156	0.5657	0.5204	0.07304	0.1981

Figure 12: Business Canvas Priority Heat-map⁹.

2.6.5. Step 5: Refinement of the CEBM canvases

In Step 5, DMO, KEA and innovation owners work collaboratively to obtain the initial CEBM canvases. This step involves using the Business Model Circularity Assessment evaluation results, key success factors ([7], pp. 66-73), and the AS-IS business model canvases as inputs to fine-tune the canvases based on established element-wise priorities (Figure 12) and ranks. The output of this process is the initial CEBM canvas, which forms the basis for further enhancements and applications.

Specifically, this step could be interpreted as circularising the AS-IS business model canvases, which may still exhibit linear characteristics to some extent. This integration is guided by key success factors which, while generic, serve as prompts for discussion and idea generation during the refinement process. Each CEBM pattern is associated with distinct key success factors relating to specific business model canvas elements. With the AS-IS business model and the CEBM rankings at hands, our goal is to systematically adjust the business model in accordance with the priority elements identified in the heatmaps and the key success factors associated with each CEBM pattern.

⁹ Numbers in the heatmap are illustrative.

2.6.6. Step 6: Business Model SWOT Analysis and Evaluation

In Step 6 of the methodology, Business Model SWOT Analysis (Figure 20 [7]) is conducted to critically assess the strengths and weaknesses of the initial CEBM canvases. This step is divided into two sub steps, each focusing on distinct but complementary tasks.

- **6.1 - Business Model SWOT Analysis:** Conducted by KEA and innovation owners, this step involves a thorough analysis of the initial CEBM canvases. This analysis serves to pinpoint the robust areas and potential vulnerabilities within the CEBMs.
- **6.2 – Evaluation of the Analysis:** Jointly undertaken by the DMO and KEA and innovation owners, this step builds on the findings from the previous analysis. The focus here is on identifying weaknesses within the CEBM canvases and determining which elements require further review and enhancement. Similar to the approach taken in Step 5, we aim to numerically evaluate the assessment to provide specific canvas elements that could be further developed in the CEBM canvases. This numerical evaluation could help to systematically refine the business models by identifying the most critical areas for improvement.

Overall, the outcome of this step is a clear identification of canvas elements that need additional attention to optimize the CEBMs. Consequently, we adopt an iterative approach to fine-tune the CEBM canvases. This involves revisiting **Step 5** to refine the canvas elements further, ultimately leading to the development of the finalized CEBM canvases.

2.6.7. Step 7: Value Network Mapping

In Step 7, DMO along with the KEA and innovation owners undertake the task of Value Network Mapping. This step utilizes the CEBM canvases as the primary input to conduct detailed mapping of material networks and value flows. The main tasks include identifying and visualizing how materials and value circulate within the network, providing essential insights into the current dynamics. The output of this process is a comprehensive understanding of the material and value flows, which brings clarity to the existing interactions and dependencies within the value network.

According to [7], it consists of two sub steps that utilizes the canvases depicted in Figure 13:

- Engaging in discussions to describe the flow of key materials relevant to the value proposition and CEBM being examined.
- Facilitating discussions to delineate the interactions among key stakeholders that influence the material flow. Additionally, mapping the nature of these relationships in terms of value being exchanged. This value mapping should ideally consider both financial aspects as well as social and environmental contributions.

Figure 13: (a) Material Flow Perspective and (b) Value Network Canvases [7].

2.6.8. Step 8: Review of Potential Partnerships

In Step 8, all the relevant actors within consortium come together to review potential partnerships. Utilizing all CEBM canvases as input, this step involves defining the desired assets, articulating the value offered, and engaging in discussions about potential partnerships by using the canvas depicted in Figure 14.

The main tasks aim to identify and evaluate partnership opportunities and foster empathy among prospective KEA and innovation owners. The outcome of this step is a detailed identification of potential collaborative relationships and an enhanced understanding and alignment of interests between partners.

Figure 14: Review of potential partnerships [9].

In the R2PI methodology, the review of the potential partnerships involves a series of structured steps. Initially, participants define “**Desired Assets**” by identifying elements missing from their business models (CEBMs) for which they seek partners, using this definition to construe potential partners based on desired assets. Subsequently, a “**Value Offer**” is developed, which must connect with the desired value of a partner and be rooted in one or more elements of the participant's own CEBM, ensuring that the offer complements or enhances partner’s value. This is followed by “**Transfer Activity**”, where participants determine how the values will be connected through specific collaboration activities, setting the stage for value integration between the partners. The final step, “**Creating Value**”, focuses on whether the newly established connections enable the creation of new forms of value that can innovate one of the building blocks of their CEBM, solidifying the foundation for productive partnership [9].

3. Towards Reincarnate CEBMS

This section presents the outcomes of Reincarnate Exploitation Methodology **Steps 1** and **2** conducted for selected KEAs 2 and 3, along with the results from the application of the **Platform Navigator** on KEA 1.

For KEA 2 and 3, the process involved the identification of CEBM patterns and the development of AS-IS business model canvases through a workshop. Each KEA section is detailed with a characterization table, followed by the identification of CEBM patterns, insights from the interactive workshops, and the outcomes of the AS-IS canvases.

3.1. KER#1, Circular Potential Information Management Platform

3.1.1. Identification of the KER

The identification of the CEBM patterns for this KEA was based on data from the Reincarnate Grant Agreement and Impact Master Plan as shown in Table 2: Initial identification of KER#1.

Table 2: Initial identification of KER#1

KER#1 CPIM	
Short Description: Circular Potential Assessment Information Management and Decision Support Tool	Background IP: The solutions will be based upon the robotic wall-climbing robotic platform (TRL-2) and commercial drone and sensor solutions.
Exploitation Strategy: At the end of the project, possibilities for establishing start-ups providing building assessment and CP-IM modelling services will be evaluated in close cooperation with the TUB Centre for Entrepreneurship. If possible, patents will be filed for base technologies and working principles to secure the IP for the solutions. A very important part of the exploitation strategy for this KEA will be the integration of non-destructive test assessments with existing norms and regulations, national and international. Additionally, the development of economic business processes will be of importance. Technologically, efforts will be undertaken to developed further solutions for the automation of the processes, such as improvements in the autonomous behaviour of the robots using BIM integrated path finding and optimization methods and by improving the mobility of the robots with novel mechatronic solutions.	

3.1.2. Detailed description of KER

KEA#1 CP-IM	
Type, Name Short Description	Exploitation Information
Type*: SaaS	KEA Manager: DMO Innovation Level: 3-4 Expected TRL: 8-9

	<p>Mainly for ICT/technological solutions: any relevant aspects re. interoperability to be mentioned? Ifc will be used which is an open file format</p> <p>Exploitation Vision: Software licensing and commercialization</p> <p>Actions: Describe here the KEA's progress done, until today, from the beginning of the project A workshop using Platoform navigator has been performed, initial discussions with relevant partners were performed</p> <p>IP Protection Strategy: Individual and joint IP, which belongs to individual partners or is jointly owned by partners working in a particular task and is restricted to those partners. Provisions for use of IP background will be determined during the commercialization strategy.</p> <p>Dissemination Information</p> <p>Which dissemination actions do you plan to promote this KEA? Presentations in relevant events, reach out to existing clinets</p> <p>What is the audience that can make use this KEA and that should be targeted by disassemination actions? Demolition companies, architects, engineers, housing cooperation, waste management companies, contractors</p>
<p>Market Analysis & Market Landscape: On which markets would you like to offer the new or improved product/services? offer the products produced by the new or improved process? A digital platfrom, mainly Netherlands, but not limited</p>	
<p>*Could be S/W, Software as a Service (SaaS), Robot as a Service (RaaS), process, methdology, service knowledge etc. **The innovation levels range from Level 1, Standard, involving solutions with well-known methods, to Level 2, Improvement, which enhances existing systems within the same industry. Level 3, Within Paradigm, proposes imporvements using method methods form other fields. Level 4, Outside Paradigm, focuses on creating new systems through scientific solutions rather than technology. Level 5, Discovery, pioneers new systems based on major discoveries and new sciences.</p>	

3.1.3. CEBM development

Identification of CEBM patterns:

When the CP-IM tool considered as the main value proposition, it exemplifies a CEBM pattern based on *access* rather than ownership. The tool is designed to provide building assessment and circular potential information management services, which can be offered through a subscription or pay-per-use model. This could allow customers to access the advanced capabilities of the CP-IM system without the need for significant upfront investment.

Development of Business Model Canvas:

In the case of CPIM, we decided to use the platform navigator¹⁰ which is an easy-to-understand guides with clear structure and 88 patterns. The goal was to use these patterns to identify the opportunities that such a platform can bring. We used their proposed canvas (Figure 15: The platform) and divided the consortium members into five groups: *value proposition and value flow, value creation, value capturing, growth, and management*. We then asked each group member to choose the relevant patterns from the pattern cards and add the numbers to the canvas.

After gathering inputs from all partners, we analysed the results to identify common themes and unique insights. These findings provided a solid foundation for understanding the potential value and opportunities of the platform. Based on these insights, we will develop a more detailed plan, focusing on leveraging the identified patterns to maximize benefits and drive further innovation. This detailed plan will guide our next steps in platform development and implementation.

¹⁰ <https://www.iot-lab.ch/the-platform-navigator/>

Figure 15: The platform canvas.

Figure 16: Value capturing (pattern 48-62) and an example of pattern 60.

3.2. KER#2, Wall Climbing Robot

3.2.1. Identification of the KER

The identification of the CEBM patterns for this KEA was based on data from the Reincarnate Grant Agreement and Impact Master Plan as shown in Table 3: Initial identification of KER#2.

Table 3: Initial identification of KER#2

KER#2 Building Assessment Robots	
<p>Short Description: Wall climbing and drone based robotic solutions to automatically assess the circular potential embodied in a building</p>	<p>Background IP: The solutions will be based upon the robotic wall-climbing robotic platform (TRL-2) and commercial drone and sensor solutions.</p>
<p>Exploitation Strategy: At the end of the project, possibilities for establishing start-ups providing building assessment and CP-IM modelling services will be evaluated in close cooperation with the TUB Centre for Entrepreneurship. If possible, patents will be filed for base technologies and working principles to secure the IP for the solutions. A very important part of the exploitation strategy for this KEA will be the integration of non-destructive test assessments with existing norms and regulations, national and international. Additionally, the development of economic business processes will be of importance. Technologically, efforts will be undertaken to developed further solutions for the automation of the processes, such as improvements in the autonomous behaviour of the robots using BIM integrated path finding and optimization methods and by improving the mobility of the robots with novel mechatronic solutions.</p>	

3.2.2. Detailed description of KER

KEA#2 Building Assessment Robot	
Type, Name Short Description	Exploitation Information
<p>Type*: Robot as a Service</p> <p>Name: Wall Climbing Robot</p> <p>Ownership: TUB</p> <p>Description: The project consists on exploiting the capabilities of a set of modular and attachable climbing robots</p>	<p>KEA Manager: TUB</p> <p>Innovation Level: Level 2</p> <p>Expected TRL: TRL 6</p> <p>Pilot test/ validation: BIM Berliner Immobilienmanagement GmbH Deutsches Technik Museum</p> <p>Which previous knowledge/expertise/technology/IP etc. has been leveraged for this KEA? Lightweight components (Drone industry), light sensor technology, BIM intergrated paths, outdoor wall climbing robots</p> <p>Why Innovative/ Exploitable? The wall climbing robot enable users to collect data for building inspection and validation of indoor environment without need to change the positions of the furniture or other components. The</p>

- sensors to be able to offer automated access to large or difficult sensing point of interests. The modularity offers to the KEA flexibility on the resource management and on the offer to the client.

robot allows access to sensing constructive elements with a lower economic barrier, enhancing the use of assessment technology to the stakeholders, since the cost is not a big issue.

Which are the input data/information? Which are the output data/information? Input data is the sensor reading point's grid and the geographic/geometric path that the robot must climb through. Output data are sensor readings from every reading point defined in the input.

Mainly for ICT/technological solutions: any relevant aspects re. interoperability to be mentioned? The possibility to use a IoT platform to support the data transmission adds value to the proposal. Existing robot communicate by bluetooth, for the new one, wi-fi connection is planned to increase the communication zone and capacity.

Exploitation Vision: Achieving modularity in both the locomotive aspect (imagine three different robots according to battery/sensor weight/climbing surface) and the sensor aspect (Infrared, camera, ultrasound?), the robot offers the possibility to sensor at a reduce price special and critical points of infrastructures.

Actions: Building and testing the prototype with Infrared sensing. Test on inside walls.

IP Protection Strategy:

TUB and Reincarnate Team still continue on improving the TRL level of the robot with collaboration with Leyuan who developed the robot.

Dissemination Information

Which dissemination actions do you plan to promote this KEA?

	<p>Direct communication via emails and phone calls. Also attending conferences or meeting with R&D institutes</p> <p><u>What is the audience that can make use this KEA and that should be targeted by dissemination actions?</u></p> <p>Civil Engineers, Real Estate Developers, and Structural Engineering Companies that apply sensing, Architects and Architects guilds.</p>
<p>Market Analysis & Market Landscape: <i>On which markets would you like to offer the new or improved product/services? (1)</i> <i>offer te products produced by the new or improved process?</i> Please indicate market segment, countries of interest, companies of interest. (2)</p>	
<p>(1) Europe, starting with countries with a higher development of sensing building assessment. (2) Building Engineering companies, Germany, Netherlands, Austria, Denmark, Spain, Italy, France. Existing Wall Climbing Robot is developed for indoor building inspection and valuation to detect the current condition of building components and materials for architecture and engineering companies. The model being worked on is targeted to increase climbing distance and communication zone that allows us to inspect outdoor environments like facades. Market segment for the robot is the real estate developers and engineering companies who want to detect the current condition of building component, part of materials to rapid detection and valuation. Within increasing climbing distance and communication zone, outdoor inspection on the building facades can be done without needing of scaffolding.</p>	
<p><i>*Could be S/W, Software as a Service (SaaS), Robot as a Service (RaaS), process, methodology, service knowledge etc.</i> <i>**The innovation levels range from Level 1, Standard, involving solutions with well-known methods, to Level 2, Improvement, which enhances existing systems within the same industry. Level 3, Within Paradigm, proposes imporvements using method methods form other fields. Level 4, Outside Paradigm, focuses on creating new systems through scientific solutions rather than technology. Level 5, Discovery, pioneers new systems based on major discoveries and new sciences.</i></p>	

3.2.3. CEBM development

Identification of CEBM patterns:

On the one hand, when considering the Building Assessment Robots (wall climbing robot) as a product that the KEA owner proposes as the main value, it exemplifies a CEBM pattern based on *Access* rather than *ownership*. As shown in the Figure 24, the anticipated key partners and resources comprise an asset management and tracking, as well as an asset management platform. On the other hand, by integrating non-destructive tests assessments aimed at extending the lifespan of the target building or

its sub-systems, the CEBM pattern can be expanded to include *Performance*, as the performance of the specific system is expected to improve.

Development of Business Model Canvas:

Prior to the interactive workshop, the TUB thoroughly engaged with the CEBM canvas questions, conducting several internal meetings with the **TUB Centre for Entrepreneurship** to refine their Minimum Viable Product (MVP). TUB found the identified CEBMs—both Access and Performance patterns—relevant but exhibited a stronger inclination towards the *Access* pattern. The workshop highlighted the importance of identifying early adopters during the developmental phase. It was noted that developing a business model early on clarifies the target market for an MVP, particularly in understanding what features the product should possess to meet customer needs effectively. This process is not merely about envisioning future potential but about grounding the MVP's development in the current technological capabilities and potential customer feedback. The discussions underscored the necessity of a common understanding of the prototype—at this stage, focusing on the core features that are currently operational and expected to be implemented within the scope of the project.

For the present, this workshop focuses exclusively on **wall-climbing robots**. The creation of this AS-IS business model utilizes the R2PI methodology, which emphasizes the importance of both a *visual* and a *narrative* description of the business model. Accordingly, the business canvas is illustrated visually in Figure 17.

Business Model Canvas (Narrative Description):

Within the scope of this initiative, this KEA's main customers include structural engineering assessment companies, real estate management companies, and construction companies specializing in infrastructures such as dams or bridges where access is restricted. These sectors also encompass clients needing both interior and exterior inspections.

Our value proposition offers **on-demand, flexible access** to our modularized climbing robots, tailored to customer needs for temporary use. This service greatly *enhances* safety by enabling the robot to access narrow spaces, *speeding up* planning and preparation while reducing accidents and injuries due to the autonomous nature of the robot. Furthermore, it facilitates *enhanced* decision-making for **material reuse** and

recycling through precise, *data-driven* insights, contributing directly and indirectly to the circular economy in the built-environment.

Customers pay for the **Robot as a Service** (RaaS) through various models including rental fees, charges based on the duration of the rental period, and additional services such as specialized data analysis. This allows for flexibility in scheduling assessments to suit project timelines and ensures convenience with easy maintenance services for the robots.

Circular economy principles are deeply integrated into our offering by enabling enhanced decision-making for material reuse and recycling through ongoing development of **life-cycle assessment** (LCA) predictions for buildings, continuous improvement in data analysis, and the modular design of our robots to ensure adaptability to different project needs. These activities are supported by our key partners, which include building owners, universities, R&D institutes, hardware developers, and microelectronic workshops.

Our initiative delivers its offerings through direct communication channels such as emails and phone calls, as well as actively engaging at industry conferences, workshops, and trade shows to demonstrate our technology and engage potential users.

The relationship with our customers is collaborative and long-term, characterized by direct interactions with real estate managers and homeowners, and iterative relationships with engineering companies, universities, and R&D institutions.

Key resources include our sophisticated software platform, a fleet of robots equipped with a variety of sensors, and our expertise in data analysis and modeling. These resources are pivotal in managing stakeholder relationships and aligning with the evolving market needs, which can vary *temporally* and *geographically*.

Our cost structure involves equipment costs for assembling on-demand robots, ongoing costs for hardware design updates, and maintenance of our electronic workshop, alongside software development and operational costs covering staffing, technology infrastructure, marketing, and administration.

Revenue streams are diversified, encompassing rental fees, additional specialized services, varying charges based on rental duration, and maintenance and support services.

Social and environmental *positives* of our model include a reduction in waste generated from construction and demolition activities, **increased** recovery and reuse of valuable materials, and **extended building lifespan** through informed maintenance and renovation decisions. However, notable challenges include potential difficulties in integrating new technologies into traditional construction practices and a possible decrease in jobs due to increased automation.

Figure 17: AS-IS Business Model Canvas for KEA#2

3.3. KER#3, Tiny House

3.3.1. Identification of the KER

The identification of the CEBM patterns for this KEA was based on data from the Reincarnate Grant Agreement and Impact Master Plan as shown in Table 4: Initial identification of KER#3.

Table 4: Initial identification of KER#3

KER#3 Tiny House Production	
<p>Short Description: Robot supported automated upgrade solutions for building components for assembling tiny houses completely from reused components.</p>	<p>Background IP: Architectural solutions for the upgrade of building products (windows, façade elements, HVAC elements) developed by 3L on the P2Endure project</p>
<p>Exploitation Strategy: Project partner 3L will develop a strategy to establish a product line for circular tiny houses using the insights gathered from the project. The most important part of the strategy will involve securing the required capital to set up an own robotic production facility to automate the methods developed within the robotic cell at TUB. The developed business eco system insights will be used to establish the business networks to get access to the required obsolete construction products and to potential clients purchasing tiny houses.</p>	

3.3.2. Detailed description of KER

KEA#3 Tiny House	
Type, Name Short Description	Exploitation Information
<p>Type*: Anything as a Service (XAAS), Systemic Turnkey Development</p> <p>Name: Recycled tiny house</p> <p>Ownership: 3L</p> <p>Description: Simple configurator for individual tiny houses offers the opportunity to create a solution for</p>	<p>KEA Manager: 3L</p> <p>Innovation Level: 4</p> <p>Expected TRL: TRL 7-8</p> <p>Pilot test/ validation: Tiny House Demonstrator</p> <p>Which previous knowledge/expertise/technology/IP etc. has been leveraged for this KEA? Knowledge about prefabricated room modular structures has been gained by realising innovative multistorey kindergardens in Germany.</p> <p>Why Innovative/ Exploitable? The systemic approach making use of recycled material, upgraded products and components for a whole building is missing in the market, production line makes use of robotic application.</p>

housing, making use of recycled material and reused products offering a price value warranty and short-time availability.

Which are the input data/information? Which are the output data/information?

Input data/information:

- Parametric BIM model that can be configured into a tiny house
- Available materials from the marketplace

Output data/information:

- Life-cycle assessment results of the custom tiny house.

Mainly for ICT/technological solutions: any relevant aspects re. interoperability to be mentioned?

The configurator or the channel through which customers configure their tiny house requires interoperability with the second-hand marketplace.

Exploitation Vision: Just in Germany there is an expected market for new housing of about 400000 units per year. This product has a potential in year 3 to realise 20% of this potential i.e. 80000 units.

Actions: At the moment this idea has reached a draft stage. It is expected that the maturity level at the end of the project will reach TRL 7-8.

IP Protection Strategy:

At the moment it is complicated to protect the system and the process based on IP opportunities. And the objective is to protect characteristic parts as points of junction.

Dissemination Information

Which dissemination actions do you plan to promote this KEA?

	<p>Publications in expert's magazines, realisation of a prototype, a coordinated dissemination with a turnkey partner. Configurator at a sales platform guided by a chat assistant.</p> <p><u>What is the audience that can make use this KEA and that should be targeted by dissemination actions?</u></p> <p>Start-up families, singles, elderly</p>
<p>Market Analysis & Market Landscape: <i>On which markets would you like to offer the new or improved product/services? (1)</i> <i>offer te products produced by the new or improved process?</i> Please indicate market segment, countries of interest, companies of interest. (2)</p>	
<p>Market segment: prefab tiny building sector, individual configuration offered, countries fitting to technical offer `DACH` i.e. Germany, Austria and Switzerland. Interested company: Gisbert Duenschede, Arnsberg, Germany.</p>	
<p><i>*Could be S/W, Software as a Service (SaaS), Robot as a Service (RaaS), process, methodology, service knowledge etc.</i> <i>**The innovation levels range from Level 1, Standard, involving solutions with well-known methods, to Level 2, Improvement, which enhances existing systems within the same industry. Level 3, Within Paradigm, proposes imporvements using method methods form other fields. Level 4, Outside Paradigm, focuses on creating new systems through scientific solutions rather than technology. Level 5, Discovery, pioneers new systems based on major discoveries and new sciences.</i></p>	

3.3.3. CEBM development

Identification of CEBM patterns:

On the one hand, when considering the *Tiny House* as a product that the KEA owner proposes as the main value, it exemplifies a CEBM based on **access** rather than ownership. As shown in the Figure 24, the anticipated *key resources* include an *asset management platform* and the *assets* themselves, with the assets being the individual components of the Tiny House system, such as *windows*. On the other hand, if the KEA owner decides to participate in the Tiny House production chain, then the CEBM patterns can be further expanded to encompass **circular sourcing**, **re-condition**, and **re-make**. Hypothetically, to incorporate second-hand windows in the Tiny House production, one might engage in the sourcing of the material itself (circular sourcing), and further process it by finding upgrading solutions (re-condition, re-make).

Development of Business Model Canvas:

Prior to the interactive workshop, the 3L thoroughly engaged with the CEBM canvas questions and exhibited a stronger inclination towards the *Re-make* and *Circular Sourcing* patterns.

The creation of this AS-IS business model utilizes the R2PI Methodology, which emphasizes the importance of both a *visual* and a *narrative* description of the business model. Accordingly, the business canvas is illustrated visually in Figure 18.

Business Model Canvas (Narrative Description):

Within the scope of this initiative, 3L's main **customers** are housing companies, digital nomads, long-term residents, elderly people, students, single families, and eco-conscious individuals seeking sustainable living solutions.

3L's **value proposition** includes affordable, energy-efficient housing that offers customizable tiny houses through an online configurator. These houses are available on-demand, providing standardized units ready for quick setup, which caters to immediate housing needs. The offering enables customers to address their key needs for cost-effective, flexible, and green living solutions. Customers can personalize their living spaces and view the lifecycle impact directly in the configurator, enhancing transparency about environmental effects. Depending on the options offered within the value proposition, customers pay for the service through purchases or rentals, with additional services available as needed.

Circular economy principles are embedded within the customer offering by promoting the reuse and recycling of materials, thereby functioning as material banks. This provides additional benefits to customers such as reduced environmental impact and participation in a co-housing community, fostering a sense of belonging and shared environmental responsibility.

This is enabled by **key activities** undertaken by 3L, including resource monitoring, activity adjustment based on resource availability, and continuous development and R&D to improve tiny house designs. General contractors and digital platform providers are key partners, to which construction oversight and material trading activities are outsourced, respectively. 3L provides its offering to customers through channels such as social media, digital and personal selling, and community building events organized by municipalities.

The relationship with customers is collaborative and long-term, with opportunities for frequent personalized interaction through the various service offerings. Sustainable materials provide the skills and knowledge for this interaction. The costs associated with these activities, particularly operational and material costs, are shared with other business units to ensure economic sustainability.

Figure 18: AS-IS Business Canvas Model for KEA#3

4. IPR Protection and Knowledge Management Plan

REINCARNATE is dedicated to maximizing the impact of its research outcomes through comprehensive dissemination, exploitation, and communication efforts. The project ensures efficient management of all dissemination activities, aiming for clear and consistent communication while actively involving diverse user groups, stakeholders, and audiences. In this context, it is imperative to develop and implement an appropriate approach for knowledge and data management ¹¹and protection for the project results, ensuring alignment with the project's Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement.

This section outlines the strategies and measures to be implemented to ensure the effective management and protection of IPR throughout the project duration.

4.1. General rules for handling the IP

The rules on the ownership and access to the intellectual property of project partners follows the rules presented in article 16 “INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS (IPR) — BACKGROUND AND RESULTS —ACCESS RIGHTS AND RIGHTS OF USE” of the Grant Agreement, as well as the consortium agreement.

Article 16 of the REINCARNATE project's Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) guidelines outlines key provisions regarding background and access rights, ownership of results, and rights of use for materials and documents received for policy, information, communication, dissemination, and publicity purposes. Background, defined as data, know-how, or information held by beneficiaries before entering the agreement and necessary for action implementation, must be made accessible to all project participants. Results, tangible or intangible effects of the action, are not owned by the granting authority, encompassing data, know-how, or information, and associated intellectual property rights. The granting authority retains rights to use non-sensitive information, materials, and documents received from beneficiaries for communication and dissemination purposes under a royalty-free, non-exclusive, and irrevocable license. This includes various rights such as distribution, editing, translation, and processing, granted for the duration of relevant intellectual property rights. The beneficiaries must ensure compliance with moral rights or third-party rights. The REINCARNATE project's IPR guidelines thus ensure transparent access to background, clarify ownership of results, and define the granting authority's rights to use materials and documents for communication and dissemination purposes.

¹¹ Knowledge management may be defined as process of capturing, developing, sharing, and effectively using knowledge. It refers to an approach to achieving objectives by making the best use of knowledge.

5. Other Potential KEA

Along with the concept of CPIM, REINCARNATE introduces a set of technical and process innovations (Table 5) in Work Packages 2 (WP2) and 3 (WP3). These innovations extend existing ICT methods and technologies from low technology readiness levels (TRL 1-4) to proven technical solutions at the system or sub-system level (TRL 6). This progression ensures that the innovations are not only theoretically sound but also practically viable and ready for real-world application. All innovations will be carefully demonstrated through at least two demonstration projects. These projects will serve as practical testbeds to validate the effectiveness and reliability of the proposed solutions in real-world scenarios. The demonstration projects will provide critical feedback and insights, facilitating further refinement and optimization of the technologies.

During the next phase of the project, these innovations will undergo a thorough examination. Using the proposed exploitation methodology, we will explore their exploitable potentials. This process will involve assessing the commercial viability, scalability, and potential impact of each innovation. By systematically evaluating these factors, we aim to identify the most promising innovations and develop strategies for their successful deployment and commercialization. This approach ensures that the innovations not only advance technologically but also achieve meaningful impact in the market and industry.

Table 5: REINCARNATE set of innovations.

INNOVATION		Description
CP-IM related innovations (WP1)	Building inspection and valuation	Non-destructive testing methods for materials and performance of products together with status assessment methods
	Interfaces to existing databases and planning tools	Interoperability technologies to instil data from various external sources, such as LCA database, national waste registries, or e-Marketplaces
	BIM for circular value flow planning	Tools and methods to allow for understanding possibilities to reuse materials & construction products beyond their initial use within a single building.
	On-site waste assessment and separation	Automated robots adopting hyperspectral imaging and deep learning technologies for material recognition upon the prior knowledge from CP-IM

Innovations to extend cycles (WP2)		Lean construction resource planning	A BIM supported process model to ensure effective and efficient resource promoting integrated planning including resources and allows for aggregation
		Strategic circular decision making for real estate assets	Methods to understand adaptive reuse potential of buildings and/or reuse potential of construction products / materials within large building portfolios.
		Upgrade solutions for construction products	Solutions for deinstallation, performance, and upgrading of construction products, such as windows, façade elements and HVAC components.
Innovations for restarting cycle (WP3)		BIM supported modular dismantling planning methods	Using functional, spatial and interface information of construction products, detailed dismantling work plans, and more general construction schedules can be automatically generated.
		Architectural design methods	Parametric modelling techniques and functional classification of systems and components the design allows for reuse of building components and recyclables to be semi-automatically
		Valuation of recycled materials	Methods to indicate the functional quality of recycled materials with a high confidence based on data-driven modelling approaches (machine learning).

6. References

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7. Appendix

Figure 19: The overview of concepts presented in Reincarnate project.

7.1.1. CEBM Canvases

Figure 20: Circular Sourcing pattern [9].

Figure 21: Co-product Recovery Pattern [9].

Figure 22: Re-condition Pattern [9].

Figure 23: Re-make Pattern [9].

Figure 24: Access Pattern [9].

Figure 25: Performance Pattern [9].

Figure 26: Resource Recovery Pattern [9].

7.1.2. CEBM Canvas Questions

Please note, the questions provided below are sourced directly from the R2PI Project. Thus, the term “case organisation” should be interpreted as KEA or innovation in our context.

Customer Segments:

- Who are the customers for which value is being created? *This may be a single segment, or multiple segments. A distinct customer segment has common needs that require and justify a distinct offer. The focus for the case study is on the most important customer segment(s) which are relevant from a circular economy perspective. Note:*
 - *Customer segments can be further distinguished if they require significantly different distribution channels or types of relationships; are willing to pay for different aspects of an offer; or have significantly different 'costs to serve' and profitability. This can be re-assessed once the other business model elements are described).*
 - *Companies which have control over recovery of products or materials at end-of-life may have customers relating to this CEBM pattern (e.g. scrap / materials management)*
 - *For organisations implementing co-product recovery CEBM patterns, customers will include downstream organisations purchasing or receiving these material streams.*

Value Proposition:

- What is the product/service bundle offered to the focus customer segments?
- What is the value delivered to the customer? *This can for example describe: customer problems being solved; and customer needs being satisfied.*
- How does the value proposition incorporate elements of circular economy? *For example: Design for circularity; circular sourcing.*
- How do these elements of circular economy drive or enhance value created to customers? *For example: Lower cost of ownership; convenience; cost/risk avoidance; reputational or brand value; reliability; etc. (Note: some of these may be hypotheses and should be identified as such, to be validated through stakeholder interviews).*

Channels:

- Through what channels are customers reached? *Channel types include: Direct (e.g. sales force, web) vs. indirect (stores; wholesalers); and own vs. partner (e.g. franchise). Describe whether these differ for different customer segments and/or value propositions.*

- What are the 'reverse' channels for product take-back or end-of-life product/material recovery? (if relevant)

Customer Relationship:

- What are the types of customer relationship used to serve each of the customer segments? *Examples include: self-service; automated; personalised; communities; co-creation.*

Key Resources:

- What are the key resources required for delivering the value proposition; operating channels; maintaining customer relationships; and capturing revenue streams? *Example resources include: Physical assets; Knowledge/IP; skills; financial; technological. These may be owned by the Case Organisation; provided/purchased from partners; or external infrastructure.*
- What are the key resources required for enabling circular economy within the business model? *These may be owned by the Case Organisation; provided/purchased from partners; or external infrastructure.*

Key Activities:

- What are the key activities required for delivering the value proposition; operating channels; maintaining customer relationships; and capturing revenue streams? *Example activities include: Production; providing value added services; operating platforms or networks (e.g. for sharing/rental).*
- What additional activities are required to enable circular economy within the business model? *Additional activities specifically relevant to circular economy may include: Design; sourcing/procurement; waste/recovered material processing; etc.*

Key Partners:

- Who are the key partners and suppliers who provide key assets and/or enable key activities to be performance? (Including those that relate to the implementation of circular economy elements).

Revenue Streams:

- For what value are customers paying? How are they paying? *For example: Product sale; service fee; pay-per-use; subscription; etc.*

Cost structure:

- What are the most important costs inherent to the business model? *These will relate to Key Resources; Key Assets; and Key Partners. Where possible:*
 - *Describe which costs are variable or fixed.*

- o *Characterise whether the business models is 'high-cost' (e.g. because it is capital or labour-intensive) or 'low cost' (e.g. because they require less assets or inputs to operate).*
- o *Identify whether the business model benefits from economies of scale or scope.*
- *How do circular economy elements have an impact costs? For example: The price of recycled/renewable material inputs may be lower (or not) compared to virgin materials; remanufacturing operations may be more labour-intensive than regular/automated manufacturing.*

7.1.3. Relevant Canvases

Figure 27: Material Flow. Source: R2Pi Project [9].

Figure 28: Value Network. Source: R2Pi Project [9].

Figure 29: Partnership Canvas [7].